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Predicting spatial-temporal assessment of threatened wetland and sensitive ecosystem for 2029 using CA-Markov chain model, Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

Spatiotemporal distribution of Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) changes, in addition to a variety of socio-ecological issues, such as decadal changes in LULC with anthropogenic activities, relationships between the physical environment, cultural landscape and human activities, are all important topics that can be studied using satellite imagery. This study used eastern part of Dhaka, Bangladesh as a case study. However, there are five multi-temporal Landsat images were used in this study which is obtained in 1991, 2001, 2011 and 2021 respectively. Among them, three are from Landsat 5 Thematic Mapper (TM) and one is from Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI) were acquired. This study explores the spatial-temporal assessment of threatened wetland and sensitive ecosystem for 1991-2021 and predicts the threatened wetland due to rapid disorganized urbanization, encroachments and renovation as well as drawbacks from agricultural development for 2029 using CA-Markov chain model. Images were classified into six classes using the maximum likelihood supervised method, where the training sample consists of at least 10 polygons and a total of approximately 90 to 100 pixels per class. Hereafter, their accuracy was measured by *kappa* statistics and overall accuracy methods. Finally, this paper reveals that the spatial-temporal assessment of wetland has been identified from 1991-2021 and predicted the next 10 years using different social, environmental and physical parameters. Wetlands are decreased from 27.22 % to 22.70 % and the settlement areas are increased from 15.06% to 32.12% within 30 years interval. If this trend continues, it looks that wetlands will permanently lose their unique traits and ecosystems, having a severe influence on Dhaka.

Keywords: Spatio-temporal, threatened wetland, sensitive ecosystems, CA-Markov model, prediction

1. Introduction

Wetlands are important for maintaining ecological, biological, zoological, hydrological, industrial, economical, and characteristics that differentiate, including subterranean rivers (Islam and Gnauck, 2007). Because of their splendor and biodiversity, wetlands are increasingly being

recognized as regions of great natural beauty (Finlayson and Moser, 1991). Human has relied on much of wetland's bio-production for years of age, including fish for protein, peatland for fuel, and lumber and stalks for construction materials (Maltby, 1986). It not only protects fragile species, but also contributes significantly to the financial well-being of millions of citizens in distant areas by providing jobs, irrigation, fuel, fodder, transportation, food, and nourishment (Islam, 2010). However, wetlands around the Dhaka city are under threatened due to disorganized utilization, encroachments and renovation, flood control actions, urbanization as well as drawbacks from agricultural development (Ishtiaque et al., 2015). Consequently, each year with the rainy season, city residents have severe water logging issues. Water logging is one of the key issues facing the City, according to a report on the Integrated Environment Assessment of Dhaka (World Bank, 2007). Furthermore, wetlands are becoming well-known as a home to a wide range of animals. Most of the wetlands are perennial around the Dhaka city which include brick fields, water shade, industries, rice field, *beels*, and ponds (Forests, 2010). Wetland habitats include canals, lagoons, marshland, paddy fields, and coastal areas, which provide a range of functions that aid human well enough and socioeconomic alleviation (François et al., 2005). The remnants of an ecosystem that formerly spanned a larger area but has gradually contracted due to human influence. Ecologically fragile, vulnerable, or extinction-threatening ecosystems exist. Local elite groups have authority over wetlands and environmentally sensitive regions. Bangladesh's control and safety status is more difficult and harsher as a result of financial, technological, cultural and political choices, and often a lack of cooperation among those fields (Gopal and Wetzel, 1995, 1999). Due to the absence of a central authority, coordination amongst the relevant entities is lacking for the oversight of wetlands in the city of Dhaka. Water logging is one of the City's major problems, so it is urgently necessary to put in place rules on land use, strict enforcement procedures, limitations on encroaching land on the khals river bank in the city, and urban and drainage planning strategies (Khan, 2001). Unsystematic usage, invasion and redevelopment, development and agricultural expansion challenges, and flood mitigation measures are now threatening the bulk of the country's designated wetlands (Nishat, 1993; Gopal, 1999; Islam and Gnauck, 2009).

The goal of this research is to map the current and future biological conditions of significant vulnerable wetlands, as well as their economic advantages in various ways. Therefore, this study sets major three objectives to fulfill the aim which includes 1) to identify the chronological changes

of threatened wetlands and environmentally sensitive ecosystems from 1991 to 2021; 2) to explore the functioning of freshwater wetlands and their importance in socioeconomic development in Dhaka's outskirts; and finally, 3) Applying geographic simulation (Markov Chain and Cellular Automata) in Land Use land cover Modeler, anticipate wetlands and ecologically sensitive ecosystems for 2029.

Fig. 1. Study area map of eastern part of Dhaka, 2023 (Source: compiled by author, 2023)

2. Methodology

2.1 Selection of the study site

The eastern part of Dhaka city was selected as a case study in this research (Fig. 1). With a local jurisdiction of 43,843 hectares, the study location is located between 23°42'30"N to 23°50'00" N latitude and 90°25'00"E to 90°35'00" E longitude. Furthermore, the majority of the site is located in the floodplains of four active rivers: Balu, Buriganga, Turag, and Shitalakshya. It is bordered by Dhaka City Corporation (DCC) on the west, Gazipur district (Tongi upazila) on the north, Narayanganj district (Fatulla upazila) on the south and east (Bhulta upazila).

There are 8 Thana and 1 Upazila under this study site namely, Demara, Jatrabari, Khilgaon, Badda, Dakshin khan, Sutrapur, and Matijhil and Gulshan thana-18 ward along with Rupganj upazila. Until 2023, it had a population density of roughly 23,234 people per square kilometer and an extremely relatively low Gross Domestic Product (GDP) around USD\$ 7,712 (Asian Development Bank (ADB), 2023).

2.2. Data and methods

2.2.1. Data

Landsat images from 1991, 2001, 2011, and 2021 were used in this study. Three Landsat 5 Thematic Mapper (TM) images and one Landsat 8 Operational Land Image (OLI) image were downloaded from the United States Geological Survey (USGS).

Table 1: Detail information of satellite images used in this research

Satellite Imagery	Path/Row	Acquisition Date	Spatial Resolution (m)
Landsat 5 Thematic Mapper (TM)	137/43, 137/44	22/01/1991	30m
Landsat 5 Thematic Mapper (TM)	137/43, 137/44	13/02/2001	30m
Landsat 5 Thematic Mapper (TM)	137/43, 137/44	17/01/2011	30m
Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI)	137/43, 137/44	31/01/2021	30m

Land Use Land Cover Changes (LULC) were further divided into six categories: rivers, wetlands, vegetation, settlements, agricultural land, and bare surfaces. This study used spatial modelling

(Markov Chain and Cellular Automata) for predicting wetland changes using LANDSAT TM. This spatio-temporal analysis using CA model has been facilitated us to predict spatial pattern of future LULC changes for the study area. In order to anticipate future change, a Markov chain model depicts the LULC change from one time to the next (Burnham, 1973). The primary data about environmentally sensitive ecosystems, wetland activities, and their critical importance in socioeconomic expansion was acquired from local people in the SE area of Dhaka city using structure and semi-structural questionnaires. Random sampling was used to choose 15 Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) participants for the study.

Fig. 2. Detailed methodological flow chart of the study (Source: Compiled by author, 2023)

Each group consisted 7/8 persons where 3/4 are males and 4/3 were females in the study site. Age, education, relationships to wetlands, wetland uses, ecosystem support, information sensitive vulnerable ecosystem, homeowners covering land tenure structure, rented property, farmland crop production and crops labeling, employment and finally, segment of the population protagonist were collected in 2021 through a questionnaire survey from the local community and various stakeholders. The research has been also based on secondary sources of data. A literature review was done to gather data, which helped to get a fundamental grasp of wetland deterioration, vulnerable ecosystems, wetland utilization, future wetlands use, and demographic information. Different national and international publications of government and non-government agencies, GO/NGO reports, and reputable research groups in Bangladesh were used to compile the literature. Hereafter, JMP, The Unscrambler X 10.5.1, EXCEL, ArcGIS 10.8, and Idrisi Selva (Clark Labs) tools were used to analyze the data. The overall supervised LULC classification performance for evaluating the quality of categorized Landsat TM images from 1991 to 2021 was calculated using kappa statistics and a misclassification rate.

2.2.2. Image processing

Following that, the geometric and radiometric corrections were made to all images using ENVI 5.5.2 software's Fast Line-of-Sight Atmospheric Analysis of Hypercubes (FLAASH). Using supervised classification, the image categorization was processed. This FLAASH tool, also called the "Radiative Transfer Model," supports lowering air perturbation on nadir viewing images, correcting the adjacency effect, and decreasing the consequences of scattering in neighboring sea surface pixels to recover substrates by minimizing radiances (Hashim et al., 2022).

FLAASH begins with the conventional equation for spectral radiance at a sensor pixel, L , which applies to flat, Lambertian materials or their equivalents and the solar wavelength range (thermal emission is ignored). The calculation corresponds to this:

$$L = \left(\frac{A\rho}{1 - \rho_e S} \right) + \left(\frac{B\rho_e}{1 - \rho_e S} \right) + L_a$$

Where:

ρ = is the reflectance of the pixel's surface;

p_e = is the average surface reflectance for the pixel and its surrounds;

S = is the atmosphere's spherical albedo;

L_a = is the radiance back scattered by the atmosphere;

A and B are coefficients that depend on atmospheric and geometric conditions but not on the surface.

2.2.3. CA-Markov model for LULC changes and prediction

In order to anticipate future change, a Markov chain model depicts the LULC change from one time to the next (Burnham, 1973). The following equation describes how to calculate the prediction of land use changes:

$$P_{ij} \times S(t, t+1) = S(t, t+1)(t)$$

where $S(t)$ denotes the current state of the system at time t , and $S(t + 1)$ denotes the current state of the system at time $t + 1$; In a state, P_{ij} is the transition probability matrix, which is determined as follows:

$$= \|P_{ij}\| = \begin{vmatrix} P_{1,1} & P_{1,2} & \dots & P_{1,N} \\ P_{2,1} & P_{2,2} & \dots & P_{2,N} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ P_{N,1} & P_{N,2} & \dots & P_{N,N} \end{vmatrix}$$

$$(0 \leq P_{ij} \leq 1)$$

P refers for the probability; P_{ij} means for the probability of transferring from present state i to some other state j in the future. P_N is the probability of a certain state at any given moment. The probability of a low transition will be near zero, whereas the probability of a high transition will be near one (Kumar et al., 2014) and (Behera et al., 2012).

2.2.4. Land loss and gain calculation

The total gain and loss of the various land cover classes were calculated in ArcGIS and Idrisi Selva's Land Change Modeler: ES. The change analysis was calculated into two time periods: from 1991 to 2001 and from 2011 to 2021. Firstly, we extracted the area between the beginning and ending years of the study period using data management tool. After that, the overlay techniques were used to calculate the net change in the area between 1991 and 2001 as well as between 2011 and 2021. The analytical toolbox utilized the Buffers and Erases tool for identifying changes

between accretion and erosion area. Finally, the total area of these polygons has been estimated in square kilometers using the Calculate Geometry Tool.

In LCM, the 1991 LULC classes were placed in the row whereas the 2001 put in columns. The cross-tabulation matrix for the changing probability helped to calculate the gain and loss of the land cover classes.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Decadal changes from 1991 to 2021

Table 3.1 shows the overall distribution in acres of LULC for years 1991, 2001, 2011 and 2021 respectively. Using Landsat 5 Thematic Mapper and Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager, Land Use Land Cover Changes (LULC) classes are divided into six categories: rivers, wetlands, vegetation, settlements, agricultural land and bares surface. The area of the river in the table1 has lost 0.24% in between 1991 and 2001. And in the year of 2011, the area of the river has reduced 0.36% compared to the year of 2001. However, the net loss of the area of a river from 1991 to 2021 is 0.85% of the total. The area of the water bodies/wetlands are 27.22%, 26.30%, 24.46% and 22.70% in the year of 1991, 2001, 2011 and 2021 respectively. This analysis reveals that the total amount of the area of water bodies/wetlands gradually decreases to 4.52% from 1991 to 2021.

Table 2: Chronological changes of LULC from 1991 to 2021.

Year	1991		2001		2011		2021	
	Area (ha.)	(%)	Area (ha.)	(%)	Area (ha.)	(%)	Area (ha.)	(%)
Features								
River	1549	3.96	1,392	3.72	1165	3.36	1,009	3.11
Water Bodies/wetlands	10127	27.22	9,544	26.30	8,384	24.46	7,269	22.70
Settlement	6232	15.06	10,722	22.15	12,887	25.57	17,030	32.12
Vegetation	10062	20.65	9,678	20.04	10,165	20.81	8,514	18.20
Agricultural Land	10603	21.65	9,474	19.86	9,105	19.28	8,184	17.83
Bare Land	5270	11.47	3,030	7.93	2,133	6.52	1,834	6.04
Total	43843	100	43843	100	43843	100	43843	100

Source: Calculated by author, 2023

This is happened due to rapid disorganized urbanization, encroachments and renovation as well as drawbacks from agricultural development. On the contrary, the area of the settlements has significantly gained which is 17.06% of the total because of the disorganized urbanization, employment opportunities, communication facilities and rapid growth of population. The study site is very close to the Dhaka which is capital of Bangladesh. Therefore, employment opportunities and communication facilities are much higher here. Besides that, due to the expansion of settlement, the area of the vegetation cover has lost to 20.65% to 18.20% in the year of 1991 and 2021 accordingly. The agricultural land has drastically changed in the year from 1991 to 2021 which is 3.82% of the total. Finally, the bare land has lost 5.43% in between year of 1991 and 2021.

Fig. 3. LULC distribution map for eastern part of Dhaka of five different period. (Source: Compiled by author, 2023)

This study reveals that the area of the five LULC namely, rivers, wetlands, vegetation, agricultural land, and bares surface have lost its area from 1991 to 2021 accept settlements. This is related to urbanization's rapid expansion, education, political factors, natural population growth, economic factors, environmental deterioration and eventually, social factors.

Water bodies and agricultural land decreased slightly from 1991-2021. Settlements are increasing slightly where in 2001 it was 10,722 ha, it increased drastically in 2021 (17,030 ha). Agriculture land as well as bare land decreased over time with the enhancement of built-up area and development activities.

Fig. 4. Percentages of land features in the year of 1991, 2001, 2011 and 2021 accordingly.

(Source: compiled by author, 2023)

In the graph above, the reflection can be seen. It is apparent that the settlement is progressing day by day, while the other characteristics are gradually fading. This graph primarily depicts only four aspects connected to wetlands and their ecosystems. Wetlands are substantially less abundant in 2021 than what they were in 1991, and settlements are expanding at a disproportionately faster rate. As shown in this chart, wetlands are currently threatened in this part of Dhaka city. The ecosystem of the wetland, as well as the wetland itself, are relatively fragile, as may be seen by looking at other features. Human unconsciousness, inattention, unnatural competitiveness with each other and possessive attitude are some of the reasons behind this. Building infrastructure by consuming as much area as possible, resulting in the ecosystem's collapse. These infrastructures, with the exception of wetlands, should be created.

Human activities, like urbanization, unplanned infrastructure development, land graving and industrialization are wreaking havoc on wetlands. Due to development, the quantity of wetland in this part of Dhaka city is steadily reducing as well. Stream efficient allocation, irrigation schemes and municipal wastewater discharge, industrial pollution and drainage from urban and rural areas are all examples of human activities that can have long-term effects for wetland ecosystems. Wetland ecosystems' physical, chemical, and biological components have all been changed, resulting in these changes. This shift in the wetland environment has had an influence on all biodiversity in the region, putting other water-based activities, such as agriculture, in jeopardy.

3.2. Freshwater wetlands functions and socioeconomic expansion

According to this study, the amount of fresh water available in 2021 is lower than in 1991, which has a significant impact on the socioeconomic landscape. All types of livelihoods that rely on fresh water have dwindled in recent years. The volume of fresh water available is diminishing day by day due to various sorts of trash. A graph depicting the quantity of wetlands from 1991 to 2021 is presented below:

Fig. 5. Percentages of waterbodies in the year of 1991, 2001, 2011 and 2021 accordingly
(Source: compiled by author, 2023)

The graph above illustrates that the quantity of wetland in 2021 is significantly smaller than in 1991, when it was 27.22 % in 1991, and just 22.70 % in 2021. From this it is clear that Wetland is under threat today for its city-centric way of life. Huge constructions are being created in diverse locations that were formerly wetlands and were inhabited to a variety of aquatic plants and creatures. All of those watery flora and fauna produced ecosystems that are now gone. This aquatic ecosystem was extremely helpful to the soil layers, allowing for the cultivation of a variety of crops. However, after the disappearance of this ecosystem, the soil around it has turned abrasive, making it impossible to cultivate.

Many people used to make a life off of this fresh water, but it is now nearly impossible. Many of the wasteland fish and other species that used to provide a source of revenue have vanished. The fundamental cause of all this life being wasted is industrial pollution. It has also had a significant impact on agriculture, with cultivable terrain no longer producing crops as efficiently as it formerly did. Buildings are increasingly being constructed on farmland as a result of urbanization, leaving essentially little agricultural activity in these areas. The city is already bursting at the seams with

employment and businesses; farming and fishing are no longer viable options. The air here is becoming increasingly contaminated as a result of the buildings and automobiles. The degradation of vegetation and the aquatic environment are the primary causes. Humans ought to plant a lot more trees and protect the remaining wetlands in order to live.

3.3. Prediction of threatened wetland and sensitive ecosystem for 2029

All of the classes can be analyzed using the probability matrix and Land Class Modeler. Row categories are characterized by LULC classes in 1991 where columns are 2001. The cross-tabulation matrix for the changing probability from 1991 to 2001 are seen in Table 3, and for the changing probability from 2011 to 2021, they are included in table-3. The improvement is obtained by subtracting the data from each group's entire column, whereas the deficit is achieved by subtracting the value out of respective group's total row.

Table 3: Transition probability matrix during 1991-2001.

Changing From 1991	Probability of Changing by 2001						Subtotal	
	River	Wetland	Vegetation	Settlement	Agricultural land	Bare land	Total	Loss
River	0.4269	0.1455	0.1252	0.0708	0.2168	0.0147	1	0.5731
Wetland	0.0179	0.293	0.311	0.1247	0.2366	0.0169	1	0.707
Vegetation	0.0065	0.2618	0.4015	0.1005	0.2144	0.0153	1	0.5985
Settlement	0.0098	0.2891	0.3313	0.1208	0.2325	0.0165	1	0.8792
Agricultural land	0.0068	0.2821	0.3292	0.1251	0.2395	0.0174	1	0.7605
Bare land	0.0067	0.2704	0.3503	0.1194	0.2359	0.0174	1	0.9826
Total	0.4746	1.5419	1.8485	0.6613	1.3757	0.0982		
Gain	0.0477	1.3964	1.7233	0.5905	1.1589	0.0835		

Source: Calculated by author, 2023

In order to predict the year 2029 using LULC map images from 1991 and 2021, transition probability matrices and transition area matrices were developed. This prediction for 2029 involved analyzing the LULC maps from 1991 to 2021 using the transition probability matrices and transition area matrices of 2021.

Table 4: Transition probability matrix during 2011-2021.

Changing From 2011	Probability of Changing by 2021						Subtotal	
	River	Wetland	Vegetation	Settlement	Agricultural land	Bare land	Total	Loss
River	0.6571	0.2884	0.0052	0.0171	0.0299	0.0024	1	0.3429
Wetland	0.0868	0.1233	0.5507	0.0416	0.1916	0.0061	1	0.8767
Vegetation	0.0054	0.0306	0.5171	0.0584	0.36	0.0286	1	0.4829
Settlement	0.0045	0.0188	0.0609	0.5863	0.3252	0.0043	1	0.4137
Agricultural land	0.0016	0.008	0.4436	0.0731	0.4647	0.009	1	0.5353
Bare land	0.0003	0.0015	0.0459	0.1766	0.756	0.0198	1	0.9802
Total	0.7557	0.4706	1.6234	0.9531	2.1274	0.0702		
Gain	0.0986	0.1822	1.6182	0.936	2.0975	0.0678		

Source: Calculated by author, 2023

Fig. 6. Prediction LULC of eastern Part of Dhaka for 2029 (source: Compiled by author, 2023)

Here, presented two simulations where 2029 is predicted based on the matrix of 1991-2001 and another simulation presented for the matrix of 2011-2021. Wetlands have been progressively declining from 1991 to 2021, and it is expected to be substantially lower in 2029, according to the following predictions. It is decreasing slightly where in 1991 it was 10127 ha, it decreased in 2021 7,269 ha. And following the prediction, its value plummets, implying that by 2029, the amount of wetland would have decreased significantly. Vegetation pattern decreased over time with the enhancement of built-up area and development activities.

Table 5: Predicting land features for 2029.

LULC	LULC 1991 (ha.)	LULC 2021 (ha.)	LULC 1991-2029 (ha.)	LULC 2021-2029 (ha.)
River	1549	1,009	1015	775
Water Bodies/wetlands	10127	7,269	5057	3249
Settlement	6232	17,030	22884	29358
Vegetation	10062	8,514	8320	4964
Agricultural Land	10603	8,184	7846	7485
Bare Land	5270	1,834	957	876
Total	43843	43843	46079	46707

Source: Calculated by author, 2023

Table 5 above depicts how the 6 aspects of Dhaka's Eastern zone would seem in the future. A probable image of a part of Mainly 2029 in Dhaka may be seen here. There are two types of predictions: one based on Dhaka's land class in 1991 and the other based on the land class in 2021. This is the outcome of combining two different types of matrixes. The results are the same regardless of the value, according to the analysis. The predictions for 2029 based on the image of 1991 and the predictions for 2029 based on the image of 2021 are quite near, therefore the correctness of the predictions may be assumed.

Table 6: Accuracy assessment of LULC class for different time period.

Land Use/Cover	1991		2001		2011		2021	
	P	U	P	U	P	U	P	U
River	78	83	83	79	82	79	81	79
Water Bodies/Wetlands	79	78	80	81	78	79	79	78
Settlement	81	78	83	78	83	78	82	81
Vegetation	80	81	79	77	78	79	81	83
Agricultural Land	79	78	80	79	81	78	78	79
Bare Land	77	82	82	80	80	81	83	80
Overall accuracy	80		82		81		82	
Overall, Kappa Statistic	0.80		0.82		0.81		0.82	

Source: Made by authors, 2023

** P= Producer's accuracy and **U= User's accuracy.

3.4. Accuracy assessment

The accuracy assessment is essential for a research project since it determines the resemblance of the classified data to the ground data. Because the ground data is collected at the field level, there is no chance that it would be erroneous and when it is combined with the classified image, it is easy to fix any errors in the image.

For each LULC class of study area, the producer's and user's accuracy varies with time. Table 6 reveals that overall accuracy is 81 and overall kappa statistics are 0.81. Because of the mismatch between the training sample points and the ground points, the accuracy value is poor; if the value is too low, the research might be identified as weak. This accuracy assessment is primarily performed on six different types of land classes, revealing favorable findings.

3.5. Model validation

The accuracy evaluation is sufficiently accurate since all values are more than 80%. From the statistics, the κ_{no} for 1991 is 0.8788 where it is 0.8965 for 2021 (Table 7). The $\kappa_{location}$ is 0.8352 for 1991 and 0.8070 for 2021. The value of $\kappa_{locationstrata}$ is 0.8352 for 1991 where 0.8070 for 2021. Last, $\kappa_{standard}$ value is 0.8320 for 1991 and 0.8820 for 2021. These are all values that are greater than 80%, which offers a satisfactory accuracy evaluation for this model.

Table 7: κ values for 1991 and 2021 to validate the model

κ Indicators	1991	2021
κ_{no}	0.8788	0.8965
$\kappa_{location}$	0.8352	0.8070
$\kappa_{locationstrata}$	0.8352	0.8070
$\kappa_{standard}$	0.8320	0.8820

Source: Calculated by author, 2023

4. Conclusion:

Dhaka city's wetland and its ecosystem are impacted by anthropogenic disturbance. Filing, grading, removal of vegetation, building construction and drainage pattern are main reason for causing the wetlands threatened lately. According to the matrix, wetland and agricultural land dropped modestly from 1991 to 2021 before substantially decreasing in 2029. Settlements are

increasing slightly where in 1991 it was 6232 ha, it increased drastically in 2021 17,030 ha. Vegetation pattern increased from 2001-2011 than decreased over time with the enhancement of built-up area and development activities. It appears that pressure of human domination on Dhaka city advancing the risk of ecological threatened. This research reveals a pattern and anticipates the future based on that pattern, which may aid policymakers in making important decisions on ecosystem preservation, landscape design and understanding the current state of Dhaka for optimal management.

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